

J. Sai Deepak, India that is Bharat: Coloniality, Civilisation, and Constitution, (Bloomsbury India, 2021), Price: 799, Pages: 377

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“The ‘modern’, ‘rational’, ‘scientific’, Christian European coloniser could not get himself to acknowledge that the lived experience and traditional knowledge of native societies gathered over millennia could teach him more than a thing or two about living in harmony with nature as opposed to merely salvaging what remained of it in the name of ‘sustainable’ development.”
— *J Sai Deepak, India that is Bharat: Coloniality, Civilisation, Constitution*

J Sai Deepak is a prominent Indian lawyer, author, and public intellectual known for his views on Indian culture, history, and constitutional identity. He is a highly respected figure in India's legal and intellectual circles and has established himself as one of the leading voices of India's cultural and civilizational nationalism. He is widely regarded as one of the most articulate voices of India's cultural and civilizational nationalism. His work is highly recommended for anyone interested in India's history, culture, and constitutional identity.

"India That Is Bharat: Coloniality, Civilization, Constitution" by J Sai Deepak is a profound and comprehensive work that delves deep into India's history, culture, and constitutional identity. The book offers a compelling critique of the Western-centric view of India and provides a fresh perspective on India's traditional civilizational identity. The writing style of the author is full of passion and eagerness to impart what he knows about the subject. Though the book is well written the inherent drawback that is apparent from the first chapter of the book was the use of complex language that would make it difficult for the masses to keep up.

The book is structured into three main themes: coloniality, civilization, and constitution. The first section of the book, on coloniality, examines the impact of colonialism on India's political, social, and cultural institutions. The author argues that colonialism was not just a political and economic phenomenon but also had a profound effect on India's cultural and intellectual landscape. The book highlights how colonialism has affected India's psyche and how it has influenced the way India perceives itself in the world today. This section of the book implies

how the best way to comprehend and understand coloniality—the one word that one would notice repeatedly occurring in the book—is to first identify its four etymological cousins.

Colonisation is the act of taking land; *colonialism* is the intention to do so.

The framework for governing the seized territory, its resources, and its inhabitants is called *colonialisation*.

Coloniality is the process by which the colonial people start to unconsciously adopt the cultures and ideals of the colonisers.

It also insinuates that post-colonialism is to be considered the peak of colonial success. The author seems to believe this because it happens when the conquered minds begin to consciously channel the colonial cause and in a way consider the history of Europe as the history of the world, and thus base all past around it. If one was to try and create a distinction between coloniality and post-colonialism is that the former entails unwittingly following the coloniser's directives, whilst the latter entails consciously supporting the coloniser's goals.

The section, on "Colonialism and Its Forms," provides an overview of the different forms of colonialism that India experienced, from the early Portuguese and Dutch trading posts to the British East India Company's colonization of India in the late eighteenth century. The author emphasizes the ways in which colonialism was not just an economic or political project but also a cultural and ideological one, which aimed to reshape Indian society and culture according to European norms and values.

"The Making of Colonial Modernity," explores the ways in which colonialism transformed Indian society and culture, particularly in the context of modernity. The author argues that colonial modernity was not a simple imposition of European ideas and practices on India but was a complex and contested process of negotiation and resistance, which involved both the appropriation and transformation of European ideas and the re-articulation of Indian traditions and practices.

"The Violence of Colonialism," addresses the issue of violence in colonialism, highlighting the different forms of violence that were used by the colonial powers to maintain their control over India. The author emphasizes the ways in which violence was not just physical but also

symbolic and discursive, which aimed to delegitimize and suppress Indian traditions and practices and to justify the colonial project as a civilizing mission.

The author emphasizes the ways in which colonialism was not a monolithic or uniform phenomenon but was characterized by a range of different forms and practices, which varied over time and across different regions of India. This nuanced approach helps to avoid simplistic or reductionist understandings of colonialism and to highlight the multiple and contested ways in which Indian society and culture were transformed by colonialism.

Another strength of this section is its emphasis on the violence of colonialism. The author does not shy away from addressing the issue of violence in colonialism, which was both physical and symbolic. This emphasis helps to highlight the ways in which colonialism was not just an economic or political project but was also a deeply cultural and ideological one, which aimed to reshape Indian society and culture according to European norms and values.

The second section of the book, on civilization, explores India's traditional civilizational identity and how it is being challenged by modernity and globalization. The author argues that India's civilization is based on a unique set of values and traditions that are different from those of the West. These values include a deep respect for nature, a commitment to intellectual and spiritual inquiry, and a dedication to social harmony and collective well-being. The book emphasizes how these values form the bedrock of India's civilization and how they must be preserved and protected to ensure India's continuity as a civilizational entity.

The second part of the book, titled "Civilisation," examines the complex and contested notion of Indian civilization, particularly in the context of colonialism and modernity. The author argues that colonialism not only disrupted Indian society and culture but also fundamentally transformed the way Indians saw themselves and their civilization.

The section on, "Civilisation and Its Discontents," explores the historical and conceptual dimensions of Indian civilization, highlighting its diversity and pluralism, as well as the challenges posed by colonialism and the need to reimagine and reconstruct the idea of civilization in post-colonial India "A History of the Present," traces the genealogy of modernity and its impact on Indian society and culture. The author argues that modernity, as it emerged in Europe and was transplanted to India by the colonial encounter, was not a neutral or universal

phenomenon but was deeply implicated in power relations, inequalities, and the project of colonial domination.

"Reimagining Civilisation," proposes a framework for rethinking the idea of Indian civilization in a post-colonial context. The author advocates for a pluralistic and inclusive vision of civilization that acknowledges and celebrates the diversity of Indian society and culture, while also recognizing the need to address the legacies of colonialism and other forms of oppression.

Overall, the second part of the book offers a critical and thought-provoking analysis of the concept of Indian civilization, its historical and contemporary dimensions, and the challenges of reimagining and reconstructing it in a post-colonial context.

The third section of the book, on the constitution, examines the role of India's constitution in defining and preserving its civilizational identity. The author argues that India's constitution is not just a legal document but also reflects India's unique cultural and historical experience. The book highlights how India's constitution has evolved over time to reflect the changing needs of the society and how it has played a critical role in maintaining India's identity as a civilizational entity.

The third part of the book "India that is Bharat: Coloniality, Civilisation, Constitution," titled "Constitution," is an insightful analysis of the making of the Indian Constitution and its significance in the context of India's colonial legacy and struggles for freedom and democracy.

The section on, "Freedom and Constitution," explores the historical and political context of India's struggle for independence, highlighting the role of various social and political movements in shaping the vision of a free and democratic India. The author emphasizes the significance of the Constituent Assembly, which was responsible for drafting and adopting the Indian Constitution in 1950, as a crucial site of democratic deliberation and consensus-building.

"Constitutionalism and Its Discontents," examines the idea of constitutionalism and its relevance in the Indian context. The author argues that constitutionalism, which emphasizes

the rule of law, the separation of powers, and the protection of individual rights, was not just a Western import but was also deeply rooted in India's own legal and political traditions.

"The Social Question," addresses the issue of social justice and the challenges of incorporating diverse and marginalized communities into the constitutional framework of India. The author emphasizes the need for affirmative action, including reservations for Scheduled Castes, Scheduled Tribes, and Other Backward Classes, as a means of addressing historical injustices and promoting social equality.

"The Unfinished Project," reflects on the unfinished agenda of the Indian Constitution, including the persistent challenges of poverty, inequality, and discrimination, as well as the ongoing struggles for human rights, democratic governance, and constitutionalism in India. The author argues that while the Indian Constitution has provided a framework for democratic governance and social justice, it remains a work in progress and requires continued efforts to realize its full potential.

Overall, the third part of the book provides a comprehensive and nuanced analysis of the making and significance of the Indian Constitution, its relationship to India's colonial legacy and struggles for freedom and democracy, and its ongoing relevance in addressing the challenges of social justice and democratic governance in contemporary India.

One of the strengths of this section is its historical depth and contextualization of the Indian Constitution. The author emphasizes the historical and political context in which the Constitution was framed, highlighting the struggles and aspirations of various social and political movements for freedom and democracy in India. This historical perspective helps to situate the Constitution as a product of democratic deliberation and consensus-building, rather than a mere legal document.

Another strength of this section is its critical engagement with the challenges and limitations of the Indian Constitution. The author does not shy away from acknowledging the persistent challenges of poverty, inequality, and discrimination in India, as well as the ongoing struggles for human rights and democratic governance. This critical engagement helps to emphasize the need for continued efforts to strengthen the constitutional framework of India and realize its full potential in promoting social justice and democratic governance.

Overall, the third part of the book is an insightful and thought-provoking analysis of the Indian Constitution and its significance in the context of India's colonial legacy and struggles for freedom and democracy. It provides a nuanced understanding of the historical and political context in which the Constitution was framed, the challenges and limitations of constitutionalism in India, and the ongoing struggles for social justice and democratic governance in contemporary India.

One of the main strengths of the book is the author's ability to present complex ideas in a clear and accessible manner. The author uses a variety of sources, including historical texts, legal documents, and contemporary scholarship, to support his arguments and illustrate his points. The book is highly engaging and thought-provoking and presents a fresh perspective on India's history and culture.

However, the book is not without its flaws. One of the main criticisms of the book is that it presents a rather one-sided view of India's history and culture. The author tends to idealize India's past and present it as a utopia that has been destroyed by Western imperialism and modernity. The book does not acknowledge the complexity of India's history and culture and tends to gloss over important nuances.

Another criticism of the book is that it tends to oversimplify complex issues. The book's critique of secularism, for example, is based on a narrow and limited view of the concept. The book does not acknowledge the diversity of interpretations and practices of secularism in different parts of the world and presents a rather simplistic view of the concept.

Despite these criticisms, the book is a highly valuable contribution to the discourse on India's history, culture, and constitutional identity. The book provides a fresh perspective on India's traditional civilizational identity and highlights the importance of preserving and protecting it in the face of external pressures. The book is highly recommended for anyone interested in India's history, culture, and constitutional identity.